

Assessing Consumer Perception, Sensory Acceptance and Nutritional Composition of Radish Microgreens

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Abstract

Purpose: Microgreens, young-tender green leafy plants, are being valued for their vibrant appearance, rich flavors and nutrient-rich profile, yet remain an underexplored area. Hence, the study was undertaken to analyze consumer perception towards microgreens, as well as to evaluate the sensory characteristics and nutritional composition of three microgreen varieties (white, purple, and pink radish).

Methods: A pre-tested online questionnaire was used to assess consumer awareness and perception using 610 respondents aged 20-35 years. To identify the barriers to purchasing microgreens, a ranking method was applied, while consumer perceptions were evaluated using a 5-point Likert scale. The sensory attributes of microgreen varieties were evaluated using a semi-trained panel comprising 20 members. Additionally, the nutritional composition and antioxidant properties were assessed across the three selected varieties.

Results: The study surveyed 610 respondents, out of which 65.58% (400 respondents) were familiar with microgreens and hence were included in the study. The majority of participants had a positive perception regarding microgreens, with 84.25% acknowledging potential health benefits. Sensory evaluation of three radish microgreens revealed that all varieties scored well for overall acceptability, indicating positive inclusion potential of microgreens in daily diets. Proximate analysis revealed high moisture, moderate protein and low-fat among the varieties. Calcium, iron, magnesium, copper and zinc were also present. High levels of ascorbic acid, chlorophyll, total phenol and total flavonoids content were found in all the assessed varieties, with purple radish demonstrating the strongest antioxidant activity.

Conclusion: Overall, results highlight positive consumer perception, unique sensory profile and high nutritional potential of radish microgreens.

Key words: Consumer acceptance, Microgreens, Nutrients, Phytonutrients, Sensory quality

Introduction

In the past decade, microgreens have risen as a valuable addition to contemporary diets, as consumers increasingly seek foods that not only promote long-term health but also offer gastronomic interest (Chen et al., 2020 and Rawat et al., 2024a). Microgreens are young and tender leafy greens, typically harvested in 10-20 days after germination. They are composed of cotyledons, stems and occasionally first true leaves (Yeargin et al., 2023). They are grown from a diverse range of vegetables, herbs and grains, particularly Brassicaceae, Amaranthaceae, Asteraceae and Lamiaceae family (Du et al., 2022). Originally popularized as garnishes in the 1980s, microgreens have evolved as mainstream health foods valued for their attractive color, intense flavor and ease of cultivation in both soil and soilless systems, such as hydroponics and vertical farming (Yeargin et al., 2023), and thus have gained acceptance among chefs, researchers and health-oriented individuals.

With shifting dietary preferences and increasing demand for healthful, convenient and sustainable foods, microgreens are being used in new innovative food products (Siddiqui et al., 2022; and Coman et al., 2025). The perception of consumers has a major impact on the adoption of any new food product. Factors such as texture, taste, appearance, familiarity and belief that it is good for health contribute significantly in framing acceptance (Laureati et al., 2024). It is, therefore, essential to explore and understand the attitudes and sensory inclinations of consumers toward microgreens, especially in India, since there is extremely limited literature on consumer reaction towards this new food category.

A handful of studies have discussed sensorial qualities of microgreens within the Indian context. Dalal et al. (2020) evaluated organoleptic qualities of sunflower microgreens treated with various post-harvest treatments. They concluded that samples treated with citric acid and ascorbic acid were more accepted compared to the other treatments. Similarly, Shetty et al. (2024) assessed the sensory acceptance of three varieties of microgreens produced in varied media by a panel of 99 participants. They concluded that spinach microgreens produced in cocopeat-vermicompost were most preferred. Around the world, various researchers have investigated the sensory characteristics of microgreens (Xiao et al., 2015; Caracciolo et al., 2020; Michell et al., 2020; and Chen et al., 2020), and the findings indicated that visual appearance plays a crucial role in determining consumer acceptability (Caracciolo et al., 2020). In addition to analyzing the sensory acceptance and consumer acceptance of a new food item, it is necessary to study its nutritional profile.

Microgreens are also gaining popularity as nutrient-dense foods. Studies has proven that microgreens generally have high moisture content, very low fat and moderate protein levels (Kowitcharoen et al., 2021), along with minerals like iron, zinc, calcium and magnesium (Balik et al., 2024). Microgreens also have a significant amount of beta-carotene, alpha-tocopherol, ascorbic acid and phyloquinone (Xiao et al., 2012). Moreover, bioactive compounds like phenols (Petropoulos et al., 2021), flavonoids (Altuner et al., 2022), glucosinolates (Lu et al., 2021; and Demir et al., 2023), chlorophyll (Stajcic et al., 2024) and anthocyanins (Bulgari et al., 2017) are also identified in microgreens. Thus, rendering microgreens a viable food product in addressing micronutrient deficiencies, especially in resource-limited areas.

Although it has a promising nutritional value, the existing literature on microgreens, especially in India, remains scarce. Hence, this study was undertaken to bridge the gap in the open literature. The present study was undertaken to understand the consumer perception regarding microgreens. Additionally, sensory attributes and nutritional composition of three microgreen varieties, viz., white, purple and pink radish, were investigated.

Methods

Consumer perception

To understand the perception and awareness of consumers regarding microgreens, an online survey was undertaken in 2023-2024. A self-designed questionnaire served as the data collection tool. The survey targeted individuals aged 20 to 35 years, a demographic that represents a substantial portion of the consumer market and they are also open to emerging food trends and innovative dietary practices. Before this study, a pilot study (Rawat et al., 2024b) was conducted. The results from the pilot study were used to determine the sample size for the present study. The sample size was calculated using a formula given by Charan and Biswas (2013).

$$\text{Sample size} = \frac{Z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 p(1-p)}{d^2}$$

Where,

$Z_{1-\alpha/2} = 1.96$ (Standard normal variate)

p = Expected proportion in population based on pilot study
d = 0.05

The calculated sample size was 344.64, which was rounded up to 400. Data collection was conducted using convenience sampling through a self-designed questionnaire distributed via social media platforms. All the willing individuals completed the sociodemographic section of the survey. The screening question in the questionnaire assessed participants' familiarity with microgreens. Respondents who selected any options from “recognize but never tasted, tasted but do not use, occasional use, frequent use” were eligible to proceed with the rest of the survey. The individuals who demonstrated basic familiarity with microgreens responded to the further questions in the questionnaire. To achieve the desired sample of 400 responses, 610 individuals had to be contacted. The subsequent sections of the questionnaire explored participants' sources of information, purchasing channels, and perceived costs. Additionally, participants were asked to rank seven constraints on the scale of 1 (most significant) to 7 (least significant). Consumer attitude and perception toward microgreens were assessed through a five-point Likert scale.

Sample preparation

This study investigated three microgreen species. The species included white radish, purple radish and pink radish. The selected microgreen varieties were procured from local suppliers at Rs. 150 for 100 grams. After harvesting, the microgreen samples were stored in plastic hinged containers at 4°C until further analysis.

Sensory evaluation

For conducting sensory evaluation, a panel of individuals aged 20-35 years was selected using the triangle test and threshold test from the Division of Food Science and Nutrition, Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan. The selected microgreen varieties were cleaned properly. The samples were brought to room temperature before being evaluated by 20 semi-trained panelists. Five grams of each microgreen were presented on a white plate, which was coded alphabetically to ensure blinding. The microgreens were rated from 0 to 100 for 12 sensory attributes, i.e., the intensity of aroma, sourness, bitterness, astringency, heat, grassy, sweetness, texture, and the acceptability of texture, appearance, flavor and overall eating quality (Xiao et al., 2015) using a composite score card. For intensity-based attributes, scores ranged from 0 (none) to 100 (very strong); the texture intensity ranged from tender (0) to fibrous (100). Before the start of the evaluation, panelists were briefed on the instructions regarding the procedure. Whereas for acceptability attributes, the scale ranged from bad (0) to excellent (100). To minimize bias, participants were seated individually in a quiet environment and instructed not to communicate with one another during the sensory session. To prevent flavor carryover, the panelists were asked to use water for cleaning their palates.

Proximate analysis

Proximate composition (g/100g), viz., moisture, protein, ash, fat, fiber and carbohydrate content, was analyzed following standard procedures of AOAC (2000). For moisture content estimation, samples were dried using a hot air oven (Ambassador hot air oven (BPI-11-12-13), BP Industries, New Delhi, India) to a constant weight. The protein content was estimated using Kjeldahl method via Kel plus (KES060L), Pelican, Chennai, India. While crude fat was extracted using Socs Plus (SCS6), Pelican, Chennai, India. Ash content was estimated by incineration in a muffle furnace (KI 180(a), Kheera Instruments Pvt. Limited) at 550 °C, and crude fiber by sequential acid and alkali digestion. Carbohydrates were calculated by the difference method.

$$\text{Carbohydrate} = 100 - \{\text{Protein} + \text{Fat} + \text{Ash} + \text{Fiber} + \text{Moisture}\}$$

Minerals

The atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) (Thermo Scientific, serial no. AA05124904, Type- iCE 3500 AA System) was used to determine the concentrations of calcium, magnesium, iron, zinc and copper. The concentration of the metal is detected in parts per million (ppm). The mineral content was expressed as mg/100g fresh weight (FW). The following formula was used for calculation (Paul et al., 2014):

Metal (mg/100g) = {Concentration of metal in ppm X volume made}/ weight of the sample

Phytochemical content

Ascorbic acid (mg /100 g FW) was determined titrimetrically using 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol dye following the AOAC (2000) method. Chlorophyll content was determined following the procedure described by Altuner et al. (2021).

Antioxidant properties

Total phenolic content and total flavonoids content were spectrophotometrically estimated by methods provided by Singleton & Rossi (1965) and Eom et al. (2008), respectively. Results for total phenol content and total flavonoids content were expressed as mgGAE/100g and mgRE/100g, respectively. The DPPH free radical activity was analysed according to the procedure of Brand-Williams et al. (1995) and the ferric reduction antioxidant power (FRAP) assay was performed according to the procedure of Li et al. (2011). Results of the DPPH free radical scavenging activity and FRAP assay were expressed as % inhibition and $\mu\text{mol AAE/g}$, respectively.

Statistical analysis

The IBM SPSS (Version 20.0) was used for analyzing the collected data. Descriptive statistics were applied to the data set, and wherever applicable, results were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (S.D.). Sensory evaluation scores and nutritional and antioxidant composition data were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) for mean comparison using the Tukey post-hoc test. In addition, sensory data were further analyzed using Principal Component Analysis (PCA).

Results

Consumer perception

The study involved 610 participants with a mean age of 25.84 ± 4.38 years. The sample comprised 33.28% males and 66.72% females. Age distribution included 46.72% in the 20-24, 38.19% in the age group 25-29 years and 15.09% between 30-35 years. Participants represented a broad range of educational qualifications, 41.14% held postgraduate degrees (master's and doctorate's) and 36.06% were graduates. Regarding occupation, 46.72% were students, 35.40% employed in service sectors, 9.34% business owners and 3.27% homemakers.

The majority practiced Hinduism (92.45%), followed by Jainism (3.44%). The monthly income of 38.03% was Rs. 92,951 – Rs. 1,85,895 and 24.42% was Rs. 1,85,895. Most participants were single (73.60%) and 25.57% were married. Dietary patterns showed 44.91% as lacto-vegetarians, 23.79% non-vegetarians, 23.76% lacto-ovo-vegetarians and 7.54% vegans.

When asked about microgreens, 34.42% were unfamiliar and were excluded from further evaluation. Among the remaining, 25.90% were aware but had not tasted microgreens, 24.59% had tried but did not regularly consume them, 8.52% used them occasionally and 6.57% consumed them frequently. A majority (85.75%) correctly identified microgreens as young plants, though 11.00% confused them with sprouts and 2.50% considered them fully

grown vegetables. There were a few respondents (0.75%) who identified microgreens as genetically modified plants.

Introduction to microgreens was a recent food product for many, with 50.00% learning about them in less than a year and 18.75% knew about them in the past 1-2 years. Whereas, 20.00% were aware of microgreens for 3-4 years and 11.25% over 5 years. The primary information sources included friends and relatives (48.00%), health professionals or chefs (26.75%), digital media (16.50%) and print media (8.75%). Regarding purchase preferences, 12.50% participants grew microgreens at home, while 21.75% and 5.00% bought them from organic shops and supermarkets, respectively. Whereas, 5.25% used online platforms and 17.50% sourced microgreens directly from farms and 38.00% never purchased microgreens. A total of 37.25% participants were unaware of microgreens pricing; among those who estimated, 17.50% believed 100 g costs Rs. 201-300, 8.75% estimated Rs. 100-200 and 36.50% thought it exceeded Rs. 301.

Participants identified a lack of awareness as the major barrier to purchasing microgreens followed by high perishability, limited availability, insufficient knowledge of health benefits, high price, personal dislike, and fear of trying new foods.

Table 1. Distribution of participants regarding perception towards microgreens

Statements	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
	Per cent				
Microgreens are beneficial for health	64.75	19.50	7.00	2.25	6.50
Microgreens consumption is trendy	22.75	48.25	20.25	5.75	3.00
Microgreens support gut health	35.50	27.75	30.50	3.25	3.00
Microgreens consumption is safe	36.75	39.75	12.00	7.50	4.00
Individuals with diseases like thyroid, diabetes, high/low blood pressure can consume microgreens	40.00	35.50	16.00	2.50	6.00
Microgreens help in repairing damage from an unhealthy diet	33.25	39.00	19.25	4.50	4.00
Excessive consumption can cause harm	21.25	16.50	40.00	12.50	9.75
Microgreens are costly	18.50	40.00	29.00	8.00	4.50
Microgreens can be considered a value for money	24.00	27.25	35.00	9.25	4.50
Microgreens should be consumed raw	21.25	25.00	37.25	12.75	3.75
Juices prepared using microgreens are commercially available	11.00	9.50	37.25	29.00	13.25
Less perishable microgreen-based products are needed	47.00	31.50	15.50	3.75	2.25

The perception of consumers towards microgreens, shown in table 1, was positive, with 84.25% acknowledging health benefits, 63.25% recognizing gut health support, over 76.50% and 75.50% agreeing on their safety for both healthy individuals and those with health conditions, respectively. More than half (71.00%) viewed microgreens as a trendy food choice. However, concerns about excessive consumption risks (37.75%) and being expensive

(58.50%) were present among the consumers. A salient finding was that 78.50% of participants agreed on the need for the development of less perishable value-added microgreen products. This highlights a notable opportunity for innovation in this particular area.

The observations reflect a predominantly positive sentiment regarding the health benefits associated with microgreens. Despite concerns related to their affordability and availability, the overall attitude remains favorable. The data points to a growing interest in including microgreens and microgreen-based food products in the daily diet.

Sensory evaluation

As shown in table 2, among the three radish varieties, pink radish microgreens scored the highest (58.60 ± 27.41) for the intensity of aroma. Intensity of sourness scored from 8.50 ± 16.65 (white radish) to 16.15 ± 26.52 (pink radish), indicating that all the evaluated radish microgreens varieties exhibited a relatively mild sour taste. Similarly, intensity of sweetness ranged from 6.85 ± 10.78 (pink radish) to 11.35 ± 13.63 (white radish), suggesting a low sweet taste among all the varieties. Whereas, intensity of bitterness (23.00 ± 23.30 to 48.30 ± 32.77), astringency (26.45 ± 23.30 to 68.40 ± 31.26), grassy (35.95 ± 27.76 to 44.65 ± 26.04) and heat (19.45 ± 29.39 to 44.70 ± 36.43) showed a wide range of variations reflecting distinct and diverse flavor profiles to each variety. The analysis of sensory attributes among the three microgreen varieties revealed significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) in only two sensory attributes, viz., intensity of bitterness and intensity of astringency. On the other hand, the acceptability of overall eating quality was rated as good (50.60 ± 22.24 to 65.35 ± 19.18), with scores exceeding 40 (Saftner et al., 2008), as shown in table 2. Among all microgreens, scores for acceptability of flavor and appearance ranged from 49.55 ± 24.26 to 61.25 ± 23.04 and 63.10 ± 28.62 to 65.50 ± 26.40 , respectively. The sensory scores for acceptability of texture across the evaluated microgreens were highest for white radish (67.10 ± 22.05) and lowest for pink radish (61.35 ± 26.03). The scores indicate the variation in acceptability among the varieties, although no statistically significant differences ($p \geq 0.05$) were observed among varieties.

Table 2. Sensory analysis by a semi-trained panel (n=20)

Sensory attributes	Microgreen varieties			p-value
	White radish	Purple radish	Pink radish	
Intensity of aroma	58.00 ± 28.02	58.15 ± 29.81	58.60 ± 27.41	0.99
Intensity of bitterness	23.00 ± 23.30^a	39.75 ± 29.93^{ab}	48.30 ± 32.77^b	0.02*
Intensity of astringency	26.45 ± 23.30^a	63.45 ± 27.18^b	68.40 ± 31.26^b	0.00*
Intensity of grassy	44.65 ± 26.04	43.55 ± 26.88	35.95 ± 27.76	0.54
Intensity of heat	19.45 ± 29.39	37.15 ± 35.13	44.70 ± 36.43	0.06
Intensity of sweetness	11.35 ± 13.63	8.35 ± 10.56	6.85 ± 10.78	0.47
Intensity of sourness	8.50 ± 16.65	14.45 ± 21.82	16.15 ± 26.52	0.51
Intensity of texture	56.00 ± 28.77	58.45 ± 28.93	61.80 ± 29.63	0.81
Acceptability of appearance	63.25 ± 25.45	63.10 ± 28.62	65.50 ± 26.40	0.95
Acceptability of flavor	61.25 ± 23.04	57.65 ± 24.21	49.55 ± 24.26	0.29
Acceptability of texture	67.10 ± 22.05	65.25 ± 28.99	61.35 ± 26.03	0.77
Acceptability of overall eating quality	65.35 ± 19.18	59.45 ± 24.08	50.60 ± 22.24	0.11

*Significant at $p \leq 0.05$, different superscript letters within the same row denote significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$

A factor analysis was performed to explore the shared variability across the twelve sensory attributes. The KMO measure of sampling adequacy was 0.72, indicating a satisfactory level for analysis. The scree plot (figure 1) suggested four components with eigenvalues greater

than 1. The first four components i.e., overall mouth feel profile, flavor profile, texture-visual profile and herbaceous palatability cumulatively explained 72.60% of the total variance. The first component (PC1) describes the overall acceptability profile with high loadings for acceptability of flavor (0.92), texture (0.88) and overall eating quality (0.91). The second component (PC2) depicts the flavor profile and was loaded with the intensity of astringency (0.85), heat (0.74), bitterness (0.65), sourness (0.58) and aroma (0.56). The third component (PC3) representing palatability was associated with intensity of texture (0.68) and acceptability of appearance (0.60). The fourth component (PC4), reflected herbaceous perception associated with intensity of grassy (0.92) and sweetness (0.24) (table 3).

Figure 1. Scree plot graph showing the eigenvalues of sensory attributes

Table 3: Varimax-rotated factor loadings of the significant principal components (PCs)

	Component			
	PC1 (Overall mouth feel profile)	PC2 (Flavor profile)	PC3 (Texture- visual profile)	PC4 (Herbaceous palatability)
Intensity of aroma	0.12	0.56	-0.12	0.09
Intensity of bitterness	-0.25	0.65	-0.14	-0.04
Intensity of astringency	0.04	0.85	0.22	-0.06
Intensity of grassy	-0.02	0.14	-0.08	0.92
Intensity of heat	-0.00	0.74	0.20	0.30
Intensity of sweetness	0.09	0.11	-0.80	0.24
Intensity of sourness	-0.18	0.58	-0.42	0.22
Intensity of texture	0.28	0.13	0.68	0.45
Acceptability of appearance	0.60	0.08	0.60	0.11
Acceptability of flavor	0.92	0.05	0.02	-0.07
Acceptability of texture	0.88	-0.05	0.33	0.07
Acceptability of overall eating quality	0.91	-0.16	-0.11	0.01
Eigenvalue	3.49	2.66	1.50	1.04
Per cent variance	29.13%	22.22%	12.53%	8.72%

Proximate analysis and mineral composition

The proximate composition varied among the three selected microgreens varieties, but there was no statistical significance, except for the ash and crude fiber. Moisture content (g/100g FW) was notably high across all the selected microgreens, with values ranging from 89.91±1.00 (white radish) to 90.60±0.34 (pink radish). Ash content, which reflects the total mineral content, varied significantly. Pink radish microgreens exhibited the highest ash content (0.86 ± 0.11 g/100g FW), followed by purple radish (0.73 ± 0.11 g/100g FW), while white radish showed the lowest (0.73 ± 0.11 g/100g FW). In terms of protein, pink radish microgreens demonstrated the highest protein content (1.86 ± 0.15 g/100g FW). Crude fibre content varied significantly, ranging from 4.40 ± 0.11 g/100g FW in purple radish to 5.56 ± 0.31 g/100g FW in pink radish microgreens. Fat content ranged from 0.33 ± 0.05 g/100g FW to 0.55 ± 0.04 g/100g FW. The carbohydrate content was higher in purple radish microgreens (2.12 ± 0.66 g/100g FW) compared to other varieties.

The mineral content of the three microgreens was analyzed to assess the and copper content. The calcium, magnesium, iron and zinc contents across the microgreens varieties were statistically different. Calcium content varied significantly among the microgreens, with purple radish microgreens containing the highest concentration (58.46 ± 0.90 mg/100g FW), followed by white radish (55.73 ± 0.92mg/100g FW). White radish microgreens had the highest magnesium concentration (29.01 ± 0.39 mg/100g FW). In terms of iron content, purple radish microgreens had the highest iron concentration (0.59 ± 0.01mg/100g FW), followed by pink radish (0.53±0.01mg/100g FW) and white radish (0.33 ± 0.02mg/100g FW). Zinc content was highest in white radish (0.99 ± 0.05mg/100g FW), followed by purple radish (0.66 ± 0.01mg/100g FW). For copper content, pink radish microgreens had the highest (0.08 ± 0.00mg/100g FW), whereas purple radish microgreens exhibited the lowest (0.06 ± 0.00mg/100g FW) copper levels.

Table 4. Proximate and mineral composition of microgreens varieties

Microgreen varieties→	White radish	Purple radish	Pink radish	p value
Parameters ↓				
Moisture (g/100g FW)	89.91±1.00	90.49±0.33	90.60±0.34	0.41
Total ash (g/100g FW)	0.59±0.00 ^a	0.73±0.11 ^{ab}	0.86±0.11 ^b	0.03*
Crude protein (g/100g FW)	1.72±0.30	1.54±0.04	1.86±0.15	0.21
Crude fiber (g/100g FW)	5.45±0.16 ^b	4.40±0.11 ^a	5.56±0.31 ^b	0.00*
Fat (g/100g FW)	0.42±0.20	0.55±0.04	0.33±0.05	0.18
Carbohydrate (g/100g FW)	1.88±0.62	2.12±0.66	1.02±0.57	0.15
Calcium (mg/100g)	55.73±0.92 ^a	58.46±0.90 ^b	46.40±1.07 ^c	0.00*
Magnesium (mg/100g)	29.01±0.39 ^b	22.96±0.80 ^a	24.34±0.66 ^a	0.00*
Iron (mg/100g)	0.33±0.02 ^a	0.59±0.01 ^b	0.53±0.01 ^c	0.00*
Zinc (mg/100g)	0.99±0.05 ^b	0.66±0.01 ^a	0.58±0.03 ^a	0.00*
Copper (mg/100g)	0.07±0.01	0.06±0.01	0.08±0.00	0.19

*Significant at p≤0.05, different superscript letters within the same row denote significant difference at p≤0.05

Nutritional composition and antioxidant properties

The phytochemical and antioxidant profiles of the three microgreen varieties varied across all measured parameters, but only ascorbic acid content, total flavonoid content and DPPH were significantly different (p≤0.05). Purple radish microgreens exhibited the highest ascorbic content (77.73±0.81 mg/100g), followed by white radish (51.58±1.25 mg/100g), whereas pink radish recorded the lowest (30.09±0.21 mg/100g). White radish has the highest

total chlorophyll content (23.08 ± 1.26 mg/100g). In contrast, purple radish had the lowest total chlorophyll. Purple radish microgreens had the highest total phenolic content (128.36 ± 32.91 mgGAE/100g), closely followed by pink radish. Pink radish microgreens had the highest flavonoids content, i.e., 2.38 ± 0.09 mgRE/100g, while white radish showed the lowest flavonoids content, i.e., 1.77 ± 0.15 mgRE/100g. Antioxidant activity was measured using the DPPH and FRAP assays, and the DPPH was found to be significantly different among the varieties. Purple radish microgreens exhibited the strongest DPPH radical scavenging activity ($78.86 \pm 1.42\%$). Whereas purple radish microgreens exhibited the highest ferric-reducing antioxidant activity (10.24 ± 1.87 μ mol AAE/g).

Table 6. Nutritional composition and antioxidant properties of microgreens varieties

Microgreen varieties→	White radish	Purple radish	Pink radish	p value
Parameters ↓				
Ascorbic acid (mg/100g)	51.58 ± 1.25^b	77.73 ± 0.81^c	30.09 ± 0.21^a	0.00*
Chlorophyll a (mg/100g)	18.04 ± 1.33	16.94 ± 1.56	16.69 ± 1.27	0.49
Chlorophyll b (mg/100g)	5.04 ± 0.99	2.61 ± 1.14	3.96 ± 0.52	0.07
Chlorophyll total (mg/100g)	23.08 ± 1.26	19.55 ± 1.56	20.65 ± 1.43	0.05
Total phenolic content (mgGAE/100g)	119.42 ± 16.75	128.36 ± 32.91	128.34 ± 21.28	0.87
Total flavonoids content (mgRE/100g)	1.77 ± 0.15^a	2.51 ± 0.10^c	2.38 ± 0.09^b	0.00*
DPPH (% inhibition)	77.68 ± 2.94^b	78.86 ± 1.42^b	68.78 ± 2.35^a	0.00*
FRAP (μ mol AAE/g)	8.30 ± 1.12	10.24 ± 1.87	9.63 ± 1.30	0.32

*Significant at $p \leq 0.05$, different superscript letters within the same row denote significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$

Discussion

The present study provides insights into the sensory acceptance and nutritional composition of three varieties of radish microgreens (white, purple and pink radish), highlighting their nutritional potential and consumer acceptance. In addition, consumer perceptions of microgreens were also examined. The findings demonstrated that participants recognized microgreens as beneficial to health, although lack of awareness and high perishability were the major concerns. Sensory evaluation results indicated that they were rated favorably for several sensory attributes. From a nutritional perspective, radish microgreens were found to possess essential nutrients and phytochemicals that have potential health benefits. Visual appearance consistently emerged as a strong determinant of consumer choice, as it conveys freshness and natural quality (Caracciolo et al., 2020). Appearance acceptability was positively rated in this study, being consistent with the earlier published results. Xiao et al. (2015) observed that acceptability of overall eating quality varied between 39.70 and 76.50, while appearance ratings were between 55.90 and 86.40 and flavor ratings were between 39.50 and 66.90. Mitchell et al. (2020) also observed high consumer acceptability among six species, highlighting the influential role of sensory attributes on preferences and purchasing intentions. Also, findings suggest that factors such as prices and availability influenced consumer adoption. Rebolledo et al. (2024) reported that microgreen varieties were rated as moderately to very pleasing in terms of appearance, color and texture, but flavor was regarded as slightly to moderately pleasing.

Comparable to patterns of the present study on unfamiliarity with microgreens previously, Chen et al. (2020) reported that 82.00% of the participants had never bought and 69.00% never eaten microgreens. In addition, Yeargin et al. (2023) observed that microgreens

were perceived by consumers to have a relatively low risk of causing foodborne illness. On the other hand, reasons like limited awareness, perishability and high price were determined to be the dominant barriers in microgreen adoption.

The proximate composition of microgreens has been reported, though considerable variation exists across species and cultivars. Sanyukta et al. (2023) examined the proximate composition of four microgreen varieties and determined that the moisture content ranged from 80.83% to 92.63%, fat content from 0.31% to 0.53%, protein from 2.43% to 3.40%, ash from 1.20% to 1.36%, and crude fiber from 1.11% to 2.40%. In another study, Kajszyk et al. (2025) analyzed four cultivars of radish microgreens for proximate composition (g/100 g FW) and reported moisture contents of 90.90 ± 0.11 to 92.49 ± 0.11 , protein from 1.49 ± 0.18 to 2.35 ± 0.03 , fat from 0.32 ± 0.02 to 0.55 ± 0.04 , ash content between 1.02 ± 0.08 to 1.51 ± 0.20 , fiber 1.57 ± 0.03 to 3.09 ± 0.02 and carbohydrate content from 1.40 ± 0.18 to 4.20 ± 0.16 . Similarly, Kowitcharoen et al. (2021), in their proximate analysis (g/100g) of fourteen microgreen varieties, recorded moisture content of 86.57 ± 1.12 to 94.26 ± 1.21 , ash 0.34 ± 0.00 to 0.75 ± 0.05 , protein 1.75 ± 0.03 to 6.47 ± 0.11 , fat 0.15 ± 0.00 to 0.66 ± 0.03 , and carbohydrate content ranging from 2.32 ± 0.01 to 7.16 ± 0.02 . The mineral content of microgreens was estimated by several researchers. Di Gioia et al. (2023) in their study of 17 species have indicated mineral content (mg/100 g FW) as calcium (41.76–143.73), magnesium (16.47–65.16), iron (0.25–0.47), zinc (0.21–0.74), and copper (0.03–0.23). In a previous work on three Brassicaceae microgreens, Di Gioia et al. (2019) observed greater concentrations, notably for calcium (109.08–171.00 mg/100 g FW) and zinc (1.91–2.44 mg/100 g FW). These are due to species-specific mineral accumulation and possible environmental impacts.

The ascorbic acid content (AA) was yet another nutritional factor reported for a number of microgreen species. Earlier, studies have reported AA concentration between 20.40–147.00 mg/100g FW (Xiao et al., 2012), 32.90–120.80 mg/100g FW (Dereje et al., 2023) and 32.72–80.45 mg/100g FW (Balik et al., 2025), in some of the varieties AA concentration was relatively higher, such as 177.58–266.29 mg/100g FW (Gunjal et al., 2024). Similarly, the total chlorophyll content, a photosynthetic pigment ranged from 12.35–112.62 mg/100 g FW (Kowitcharoen et al., 2021) and 793.83–1391.44 $\mu\text{g/g}$ FW (Marchioni et al., 2021) to 19.60–281.70 mg/100 g DW (Stajcic et al., 2024). In this study, all these parameters aligned with the previous studies.

The phenol content in microgreens in previous researches was estimated from 49.30–811.20 mgGAE/100g FW (Dereje et al., 2023), 9.22–268.99 mgGAE/100g FW (Kowitcharoen et al., 2021), and 1.02–3.63 mgGAE/g FW (Marchioni et al., 2021). Similarly, the total flavonoids content also differed significantly, ranging between 1.10–6.50 mg/100 g FW (Ghoora et al., 2020), 1.90–7.57 mgQE/100g (Sanyukta et al., 2023) and (111.66–672.17 mgQE/100g DW) (Altuner et al., 2022). The antioxidant activity of microgreens, determined by antioxidant assays such as DPPH and FRAP, show considerable variability. Sanyukta et al. (2023) registered DPPH scavenging activity of 46.30% to 90.60% across the tested varieties. FRAP values of 2.1–8.6 mmol Fe^{2+} /g FW (Marchioni et al., 2021), 7.00–38.70 μmol Fe^{2+} /g (Ghoora et al., 2020), and 22.80–54.19 mM AEAC/1000 g DW (Acharya et al., 2021) were reported previously. The antioxidant activity in the current study aligned with previous studies. The difference in the nutritional content may be caused by the varying pre and post-harvest treatments (Zhang et al., 2021).

Conclusion

This study indicates that radish microgreens are not only highly accepted for their sensory qualities but also provide immense nutritional and functional benefits. Consumer data reflected a favorable perception of microgreens as healthy foods but with low knowledge and problems such as price, perishability, and accessibility being the stumbling blocks. Sensory testing

affirmed acceptability overall for all types, with variety differences contributing to unique flavor profiles. Nutritional study emphasized the high content of radish microgreens with essential minerals, vitamins, phenolics, and antioxidants to warrant their inclusion in preventing micronutrient deficiency. Purple radish microgreens of tested varieties possessed superior ascorbic acid and antioxidant capacity, and pink radish contained higher protein and fiber. The overall results in this regard pave the way toward the potential of microgreens as environmentally friendly, nutrient-rich foods for wider consumer uptake. Future research must aim at developing value-added, less perishable food items based on microgreens that can expand availability and access into food baskets of mainstream consumerism, particularly to emerging economies like India.

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